

"Higher Education in India-Present Scenario and Future Perspectives for Value Based Education"

28th Feb. to 1st March, 2015

- ◆ There is a need for training all stakeholders in ICT,
- ◆ The cost of hardware and software can be very high.

Thus successful implementation of ICT has potential of influencing and empowering teachers and supporting to interact with students in learning. A proper controls and licensing is also needed so that accountability, quality assurance, accreditation and consumer protection can be addressed. This will lead to accessibility and quality in higher education.

THE ROLE OF ICT IN INSTITUTIONAL QUALITY IMPROVEMENT AND VALUE BASED TEACHING-LEARNING

Dinesh C. Sharma

Deptt. of Zoology, K.M. Govt. Girls P.G. College, Badalpur, GB Nagar

ABSTRACT

We are now living in the era of technology and technology affected all part of our life dramatically and now it becomes the integral part of our life. Also the area of education has not remained untouched. We are still in the initial stages of integrating ICT in teaching-learning process. Though it is limited by a number of barriers, there are many factors influencing the use of ICT to make teaching learning effective in higher institutions of learning in India. ICT is an electronic means of capturing, processing, storing, communicating information. The use of ICT in the classroom teaching-learning is very important for it provides opportunities for teachers and students to operate, store, manipulate, and retrieve information, encourage independent and active learning, and self-responsibility for learning such as distance learning, motivate teachers and students to continue using learning outside school hours, plan and prepare lessons and design materials such as course content delivery and facilitate sharing of resources, expertise and advice. This versatile instrument has the capability not only of engaging students in instructional activities to increase their learning, but of helping them to solve complex problems to enhance their cognitive skills. ICT includes computers, the internet, telephone, television, radio and audio-visual equipment. In broad sense ICT is any device and application used to access, manage, integrate, evaluate, create and communicate information and knowledge. Digital technology is included in this definition as services and applications used for communication and information processing functions associated with these devices.

Previously, student used to spend their time in library searching for information in books and journals. Now a days required information is just a click away from them, they use web search engines such as yahoo, Google, MSN, Wikia Search, Yandex etc and figure out the web sites containing the desired information. Most of the youth are familiar with Facebook, twitter, WhatsAap, hike, viber and using them for various purposes. The information sharing has become very easy due to access on World Wide Web (www) as the world persons and their knowledge attach to each other by a web and can be transferred to each other. Technology-integrated education is still a dream at all levels of education in India. Though computers are available in most of the educational institutes now a days, however these are mostly used to learn about computers. Rarely they are used as tools for the teaching and learning of other curriculum areas. With the evolution of computer, software's and internet the traditional education tools are going to change without affecting the basic goals of education. The opportunity to use computers for teaching and

**"Higher Education in India-Present Scenario and Future Perspectives
for Value Based Education"
28th Feb. to 1st March, 2015**

learning should not be a privilege. It should be a right, just as it is only right that children should have access to books, pens and paper. The innovations that ICT has brought in teaching-learning process include: E-learning, e-communication, quick access to information, online student registration, online advertisement, reduced burden of keeping hardcopy, networking with resourceful persons, etc. However, the presence of all these factors increased the chance of excellent integration of ICT in teaching-learning process. Therefore, the training of teaching staff in the pedagogical issues and administrators in administration should be increased if teachers and administrators are to be convinced of the value of using ICT in their teaching-learning process and administration. Use of ICT for Institutional Quality improvement is the demand of day and students of 21st century.

The Ministry of HRD is presently implementing the National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology (NMEICT) to leverage the potential of ICT, in teaching and learning process for the benefit of all the learners in Higher Education Institutions in any time anywhere mode. Under the Mission, more than 700 courses in various disciplines in engineering and science are available on-line under National Programme on Technology Enhanced Learning (NPTEL). E-content for undergraduate subjects has also been generated by the Consortium of Educational Communication (CEC) in collaboration with its Media Centers. Over 100 Virtual Labs in 9 Engineering & Science disciplines, comprising about 770 experiments are currently ready for use and available. 1500 Spoken Tutorials are available on line. More than 200 courses for design have been created.

The use of ICT in teaching-learning process is a relatively new phenomenon and it has been the educational researchers' focus. The effective integration of this technology into classroom practices poses a challenge to teachers and administrators. This presentation aimed at finding out the factors influencing use of ICT to make teaching learning effective in higher institutions of learning in U.P. and identifying the innovations that ICT has brought into teaching-learning process, particularly in higher institutions of learning in U.P.

The teaching staff and administrators had a strong desire to integrate ICT into teaching-learning processes. The innovations that ICT has brought in teaching-learning process include: E-learning, e-communication, quick access to information, online student registration, online advertisement, reduced burden of keeping hardcopy, networking with resourceful persons, etc. However, the presence of all these factors increased the chance of excellent integration of ICT in teaching-learning process. Therefore, the training of teaching staff in the pedagogical issues and administrators in administration should be increased if teachers and administrators are to be convinced of the value of using ICT in their teaching-learning process and administration.

We need ICT in education system---

- ◆ To provide world-class quality education
- ◆ To fulfill the demands of huge young population
- ◆ To provide job oriented education
- ◆ To make higher education system transparent
- ◆ To protect our environment by saving papers, ink, animals etc

"Higher Education in India-Present Scenario and Future Perspectives for Value Based Education"

28th Feb. to 1st March, 2015

- ◆ To make Teaching-Learning more effective and
- ◆ To fulfil the requirement of increasing population
- ◆ To ensure transparency- Admission to examination, Purchasing
- ◆ To ensure Eco-friendly approach- Less use of paper help us to protect trees, Virtual lab and dissection are also ecofriendly approach. Less requirement of printed material is also ecofriendly approach
- ◆ To ensure physical presence of students and staff in campus by using biometric attendance- Improve quality of teaching (If teachers are in campus as per direction of UGC, then it will results in fruitful output and student teachers ratio (GER can also improve by opening Study centers of open university).
- ◆ To protect environment (Eco-friendly)

ICT is the only tool which can make

- ◆ Effective & interesting Teaching-Learning
- ◆ Effective and transparent administration of
- ◆ Higher education Institutions, which results in
- ◆ Job assured quality education

Factors affecting use of ICT in Higher education institutions

Teachers attitude- Successful initiate and implement ICT in college/university program depends strongly on teachers' support and attitudes. Among the factors that influence successful integration of ICT into teaching are teachers' attitudes and beliefs towards technology. Research has shown that teachers' attitudes towards technology influence their acceptance of the usefulness of technology and its integration into teaching. Teachers' computer experience relates positively to their computer attitudes. The more experience teachers have with computers, the more likely that they will show positive attitudes towards computers.

ICT Competence- Computer competence is defined as being able to handle a wide range of varying computer applications for various purposes. Teachers computer competence is a major predictor of integrating ICT in teaching. Evidence suggests that majority of teachers who reported negative or neutral attitude towards the integration of ICT into teaching and learning processes lacked knowledge and skills that would allow them to make "informed decision". Teachers with more experience with computers have greater confidence in their ability to use them effectively. Teachers competence relate directly to confidence. Teachers' confidence also relate to their perceptions of their ability to use computers in the classroom, particularly in relation to their children's perceived competence.

Computer Self-Efficacy- Self-efficacy is the confidence that individual has in his/her ability to do the things that he/she strives to do. Thus teachers confidence refers both to the teachers perceived likelihood of success on using ICT for educational purposes and on how far the teacher perceives success as being under his or her control. Teachers competence with computer technology is a key factor of effective use of

**"Higher Education in India-Present Scenario and Future Perspectives
for Value Based Education"
28th Feb. to 1st March, 2015**

ICT in teaching. Teachers feel reluctant to use computer if they lack confidence. "Fear of failure" and "lack of ICT knowledge" have been cited as some of the reasons for teachers? lack of confidence for adopting and integrating ICT into their teaching.

Professional development- Teachers professional development is a key factor to successful integration of computers into classroom teaching. Several studies have revealed that whether beginner or experienced, ICT-related training programs develop teachers competences in computer use, influence teachers attitudes towards computers as well as assisting teachers reorganize the task of technology and how new technology tools are significant in student learning.

Accessibility- Access to ICT infrastructure and resources in colleges is a necessary condition to the integration of ICT in education . Effective adoption and integration of ICT into teaching in colleges depends mainly on the availability and accessibility of ICT resources such as hardware, software, etc. Obviously, if teachers cannot access ICT resources, then they will not use them. Therefore, access to computers, updated software and hardware are key elements to successful adoption and integration of technology

Technical support- It is observed that the breakdown of a computer causes interruptions and if there is lack of technical assistance, then the regular repairs of the computer will not be carried out which resulting in teachers not using computers in teaching. Similarly, it is also crucial to provide the colleges with technical support with regard to repair and maintenance for the continue use of ICT in colleges. Therefore, if there is no technical support for teachers, they become frustrated resulting in their unwillingness to use ICT. Even though, lack of technical support discourages teachers from adopting and integrating technology in classrooms.

Leadership Support- Though infrastructure support is imperative, college technology leadership is a stronger predictor of teachers? use of computer technology in teaching. It is observed that a leader who implements technology plans and also shares a common vision with the teachers stimulate them to use technology in their lessons. Schiff and Solmon suggest that for effective utilization of ICT by teachers, there is the need for a strong leadership to drive a well-designed technology plans in colleges

Pressure to use Technology- One of the strongest factors between colleges in teachers' use of technology is the perceived pressure to use technology. Pressure to use technology indicates that teachers feel the expectation from others to use technology in classrooms. As technologies develop, teachers continue to be faced with increasing pressure to integrate technology into their teaching practices. Thus, it is important for teachers to know how to cope effectively with the pressure because the teacher is the key to effective integrate technology in classrooms

Government policy on ICT literacy- Policy and planning are important in identifying the aims of using ICT in education and in determining priorities in allocating resources Govt. have to set up groups of ICT friendly teachers at State, University and college level for effective integration of ICT in teaching and administration of H.E. institutions. Govt. should develop state level website to integrate and sharing of lectures, eBooks, webinars etc., so they are available to students everywhere, anytime. This will decrease the load of buying more books.

